

Research paper

Economic feasibility of Pumped Hydropower Storage in a European open-pit lignite mine

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ABSTRACT

Addressing the challenges of sustainable energy transition and resource repurposing by transforming open-pit coal mines into Hybrid Pumped Hydropower Storage (HPHS) facilities remains highly relevant. While numerous studies have explored the technical and economic feasibility of PHS, few have assessed site-specific economic risks in repurposing exhausted lignite mines for HPHS. A dynamic techno-economic simulation model was applied to evaluate the financial benefits of a potential 1,107 MWh installation in a exhausted Greek lignite mine. This study combines a dynamic simulation model with historical market data and structured risk assessment to demonstrate the financial viability of HPHS in repurposed lignite mine sites. Charging and discharging schemes were derived from historical energy market data. A retrospective simulation for the period of 2015–2024, based on site-specific parameters, was used to calculate revenues, expenditures, and profits. The simulated operation in the Greek energy market shows an average price spread of 55 €/MWh over the years 2022–2024. This results in the key indicators Net Present Value (112.33 M€), Internal Rate of Return (5.65%), Discount Payback Period (12 years), and Levelised Cost of Storage (54–61 €/MWh), all of which confirm financial viability over a 30-year operational period. A positive Net Present Value is already achieved based on an average annual energy price spread of approximately 37.28 €/MWh. The undertaken sensitivity analysis highlights the importance of economic planning and cost management. HPHS projects can provide economic energy storage solutions and benefit from stable policy support, such as feed-in tariffs and subsidies.

1. Introduction

The phase-out of nuclear power and coal combustion for energy production, along with the EU's energy transition plan aiming at net-zero emissions by 2050, is triggering a shift towards renewable sources such as solar (PV) and wind for electricity generation [1,2]. The challenge of using variable renewable energy sources (vRES) is that they are not dispatchable due to their weather-dependent nature and cannot consistently produce energy at all hours of the day. Thus, solar and wind parks are vRES and difficult to align with the grid demand. As vRES use is expanding, global renewable capacity additions totalled approximately 507 Gigawatts (GW) in 2023 and are expected to reach 666 GW in 2024 [3,4]. This expansion leads to challenges in power system operations, including surplus energy production during peak generation periods [5]. A continuous and reliable energy supply requires extended storage capacities due to the variability and intermittency of vRES [6].

GW-scale storage capacities must be established by 2035 to meet the EU climate targets and achieve a fully renewable electricity mix by 2050 [7].

Current technologies comprise short- (e.g., flywheel mass storage), mid- (e.g., battery storage power plants, smaller pumped storage) and long-term storage (larger pumped-hydro storage plants, Power-to-X) [6, 8], while battery storage is widely used due to its compactness and affordability [7,9]. In 2023, 42 GW of battery storage capacity were added globally, reaching 85 GW, and projections exceed 110 GW by 2025 [10]. Recent studies highlight the ongoing importance of larger systems such as Pumped Hydropower Storage (PHS). Yang et al. [11] analyse the role of PHS in enhancing the stability and flexibility of clean energy systems. Elmasides et al. [12] propose a power management strategy for PV-based hybrid systems integrating battery and hydrogen storage. Altea and Yanagihara [13] provide a comparative assessment

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Nomenclature

Abbreviations		Units	
CAPEX	Capital Expenditures	kW	Kilowatt
DEM	Digital Elevation Model	MW	Megawatt
DPP	Discount Payback Period	MW _{peak}	Megawatt peak
EU	European Union	GW	Gigawatt
GIS	Geographical Information System	kWh	Kilowatt hours
GP	Grid Price	MWh	Megawatt hours
HPHS	Hybrid Pumped Hydropower Storage	GWh	Gigawatt hours
		TWh	Terawatt hours
IRR	Internal Rate of Return	m ³ /s	Cubic meters per second
LCOS	Levelised Cost Of Storage	kg/m ³	Kilograms per cubic meter
LRP	Land Repurposing Planning	m	Meters
MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision Making	km ²	Square kilometers
NPV	Net Present Value	hrs:min	Hours:minutes
M€	Million Euros		
OPEX	Operational Expenditures		
p.a.	per annum		
PHS	Pumped Hydropower Storage		
PHES	Pumped Heat Energy Storage		
PPC	PPC Public Power Corporation S.A.		
PV	Photovoltaic		
RSHP	Reservoir hydropower		
RL	Residual Load		
SL	Storage Level		
vRES	variable Renewable Energy Sources		
Symbols			
B	Benefits (€)		
c_{el}	Cost of electricity (€)		
CF_n	Cashflows (€)		
i	Discount factor (%)		
N	Lifecycle (Years)		
r	Interest rate (%)		
R_t	Recovery value (€)		
t	Time (Years)		
W_{in}	Annual electricity input (GWh)		
W_{out}	Annual energy output (GWh)		

of the energy, exergy, and environmental performance of PHS and hydrogen storage systems. De Carne et al. [6] present a comprehensive review of storage technologies, highlighting the role of PHS in ensuring secure energy supply. The global status report by REN21 [14] confirms the growing significance of PHS and other storage technologies in the context of global energy transition trends.

Although batteries are efficient for short-term energy storage, they have limited capacity and lifespan. Battery systems for surplus energy operate at round-trip energy conversion efficiencies between 65% to 95%, with lithium-ion batteries typically achieving 85% to 95% [15]. In contrast, PHS offers advantages in capacity and duration. The technology can store energy from hundreds of megawatt hours (MWh) to several gigawatt hours (GWh) over periods of 6 to over 50 h [16]. These systems deliver utility-scale energy storage with round-trip efficiencies often exceeding 80% and reaching up to 90% under optimal conditions, which are higher than those of most state-of-the-art battery technologies. This makes PHS suitable for balancing electricity supply and demand, especially for vRES. Recent studies further confirm the technical and economic viability of PHS in enabling fully renewable energy systems. Yang et al. [11] highlight its role in stabilising power grids and supporting the integration of variable renewable energy sources, while Blakers et al. [17] demonstrate its potential to balance supply and demand in 100% renewable projections.

At the end of 2024, the globally installed capacity of PHS reached approximately 189 GW, representing a 5% increase over the previous year [18]. In parallel, global hydropower generation increased

significantly, rising from 4180 TWh in 2023 to about 4578 TWh in 2024. In Europe, the installed PHS capacity reached approximately 56 GW in 2024, contributing to a total European hydropower capacity of 263 GW [18,19]. The PHS project pipeline is robust, amounting to 52.9 GW across Europe, supported by EU policies and national mechanisms aiming to enhance grid flexibility and integrate vRES. Europe's hydropower generation increased to 680 TWh in 2024, driven by the growing integration of renewables [18]. In addition to existing installations, around 14 GW of new energy storage capacity is currently under construction across Europe, including 2.7 GW of PHS [20].

The concept of Hybrid Pumped Hydropower Storage (HPHS) combines local vRES with the grid, creating a more efficient and flexible energy storage system [21]. HPHS stores excess energy when needed to avoid curtailment in wind and photovoltaic system operations, supporting grid stability. Since PHS is a mature technology, wind and solar energy can be integrated with it to enhance flexibility and reliability, and manage sudden demand shifts [22]. A schematic representation of the HPHS system in both pumping and generation modes is provided in [23], illustrating the key components and layout relevant to this study.

PHS can even complement or substitute nuclear and fossil fuel plants for dispatching electricity [24]. Another advantage of PHS is cost reduction: power purchases can be minimised and emissions are lowered, when it is paired with renewables [25]. Hydropower plants also have higher lifetimes — typically up to 40–60 years — than

other energy storage systems [26]. Different studies investigated efficiency, costs, maturity and viability of PHS versus battery storage systems [7,24]. Shabani et al. [27] compared PV-wind-battery storage with PV-wind-micro PHS, showing higher reliability and benefits of battery systems, but also higher oversupply and life cycle costs under low Loss of Power Supply Probability (LPSP) conditions. Mahmoud et al. [28] highlight PHS as a mature, efficient, and cost-effective mechanical energy storage option when integrated with wind and solar systems. Javed et al. [29] demonstrate the benefits of PHS in large-scale applications, particularly in enhancing system stability and economic feasibility. Similarly, Biswas and Kumar [30] show that PHS reduces lifecycle costs and improves reliability in hybrid systems compared to battery-only configurations.

Alili and Mahmoudimehr [31] conducted a techno-economic assessment of integrating hydrogen energy storage into a hybrid PV and PHS system, exploring potential economic and technical benefits. Their study provides insights into how hydrogen storage can enhance the efficiency and reliability of vRES. These kind of combinations can extend the operator's flexibility and may provide economic benefits through smart integration and technical coordination [21].

Following the planned phase-out of coal mining in Europe, exhausted open-pit mines can be repurposed for energy storage. Several studies have explored this concept as a potential solution for storing surplus renewable energy. Weber et al. [32] provide a global atlas which is supposed to support identifying mining sites suitable for PHS repurposing. Liu et al. [33] integrate mine planning with post-closure storage potential. Bhimaraju et al. [34] conduct a feasibility study of a hybrid solar PV and pumped hydropower storage system using an abandoned open-cast coal mine in India, showing the system's technical viability and economic benefits. PHS-related policy and socio-economic aspects of regional transitions are discussed by Loewen [35]. Environmental considerations of pit lake development are analysed by Louloudis et al. [36] and Schnepfer et al. [37,38]. Wessel et al. [39] and Menéndez and Loredó [40] assess techno-economic potentials of mine-integrated PHS systems. In addition, Saha et al. [41] demonstrate that long-duration PHS in closed subsurface coal mines can be economically viable under favourable conditions, with costs and profitability strongly influenced by site-specific factors such as mine geometry and refurbishment requirements. Similarly, Madlener and Specht [42] show that, despite higher uncertainties in subsurface settings, capital investment and geological conditions are decisive for feasibility, yet competitive cost structures are achievable at suitable mine locations. Finally, the JRC [43] report outlines EU-level strategies for coal region transitions and storage deployment.

Beyond these economic benefits, repurposing former mining sites for HPHS also supports environmental rehabilitation and new opportunities for local communities, as shown in case studies for Poland and Greece [44]. Quaranta et al. [45] estimate that repurposed mines could add around 3 TWh of technical storage capacity in the EU. A key advantage is the availability of infrastructure, such as electricity transmission lines, water management, roads, and social licenses, reducing costs and environmental impact [46]. In addition to geotechnical stability, the safe operation of PHS in exhausted open-pit lignite mines depends on water management. This includes addressing complex hydrogeological and hydrochemical challenges associated with groundwater interactions, seepage, and reservoir water quality. Pujades et al. [47] demonstrate that groundwater exchange between mine reservoirs and surrounding aquifers can reduce system efficiency through seepage losses, emphasising the importance of effective hydrogeological management. PHS installations may alter regional groundwater flow patterns [48], while system operations can induce hydrochemical changes, including increased oxygen partial pressure and related risks of scaling, corrosion, or acid mine drainage in sulfide-rich basins [49]. Recent findings highlight that sufficient natural buffering through calcite-rich sediments can reduce the risk of acidification and protect infrastructure and aquifers in post-mining environments [37,38,50].

Reusing at least one existing reservoir further cuts and defers investments into new infrastructure [34]. However, site-specific designs remain critical for any project's viability. CAPEX associated with constructing greenfield PHS plants vary across countries, typically ranging from 470 to 3000 €/kW, with power-related CAPEX referring to installed peak capacity, as reported in various techno-economic and comparative studies [51–55]. The present study adopts elements of the methodological approach outlined by Wessel et al. [39], extending it through a dynamic consideration of historical market data.

Smallbone et al. [56] and Jülch [57] analysed the economic feasibility of energy storage systems using the Levelised Cost of Storage (LCOS) method, which compares technologies based on CAPEX, Operational Expenditures (OPEX) and lifespan. Their findings indicate that PHS is among the most economically viable options for utility-scale energy storage, and that it has competitive LCOS. Similarly, Mitali et al. [58] highlight PHS as the most widely used storage technology, emphasising its high capacity and efficiency for grid integration as well as vRES management.

The innovative contribution of the present study is the analysis of technical and operational data of a prospective HPHS implementation at the Kardias open-pit coal mine in Greece, by means of a dedicated dynamic mathematical model to integrate historical market data and evaluate potential economic risks. The presented methodology can be applied to further case studies to assess the economic viability, support decision-making, and help operators to optimise the benefits of energy storage systems.

In an internal workshop within the EU ATLANTIS project, 43 site-specific economic risks were identified and classified according to their impacts on CAPEX, OPEX, energy generated, operational time, and interest rates. The sensitivity analysis undertaken in the present study explores how these risks may influence HPHS profitability. Key economic indicators such as Net Present Value (NPV), Internal Rate of Return (IRR) and Discount Payback Period (DPP) were used to evaluate performance. The LCOS method was applied to assess the cost-effectiveness of HPHS and to enable comparison with other energy storage technologies. Furthermore, the impact of potential subsidies on the economic viability of HPHS was examined.

While numerous studies have explored the technical and economic feasibility of PHS, few have assessed site-specific economic risks in repurposing exhausted open-pit coal mines for HPHS. We hypothesise that financial viability of implementing HPHS at such sites can be also demonstrated based on real-world historical data along with a structured economic risk assessment. The present study extends the documented state-of-the-art economic assessment methodologies by providing a dynamic decision-support approach for mine repurposing in the context of utility-scale energy storage in Europe. The findings of the present study are useful for policy-makers, energy producers and providers, and investors for making informed decisions on implementing sustainable energy storage solutions.

2. Materials and methods

This section outlines the methodological approach used to evaluate the economic viability of implementing a HPHS system at the exhausted Kardias lignite mine in Greece. It includes a description of the study area, the applied simulation model and data sources. Furthermore, model parametrisation and the key economic indicators used for the evaluation are presented.

2.1. Study area

The Kardias Lignite Mine is located in the Ptolemais basin in Western Macedonia, northern Greece. The region features a geological structure predominantly characterised by east–west trending normal Quaternary faults [59]. The basin encompasses an approximate area of 600 km²

Fig. 1. Digital elevation model (DEM) of the Kardia mine area, Greece, showing the locations of the PHS upper and lower reservoirs. Flat terrain between elevations +650 m and +680 m could be repurposed for uses such as PV parks or agriculture. (Project Coordinate Reference System: GGRS87/Greek Grid).

and is filled with lake sediments from the late Miocene to Pleistocene, exceeding 20 km in both length and width. The sediments include lignite and alluvial deposits, with a combined thickness of up to 600 m [60]. Lignite has been mined in the Ptolemais mines for over 60 years [61], whereby the Public Power Corporation S.A. (PPC) currently operates two open-pit lignite mines: Mavropigi and South Field. The recently exhausted Kardia mine (in 2021), where the HPMS plant is being projected [36], is located in the centre of the mining area (Fig. 1). The mine has reserves of 273 million tons of coal as of January 2020, not exploitable under the current economic and environmental conditions, and supplied a 1250 MW lignite-fired power plant for almost 40 years [36]. The digital elevation model (DEM) indicates that the Kardia mine is an open excavation with elevations ranging from 471 to 868 meters above sea level (a.s.l.) [36]. In late 2023, backfilling began to stabilise the slopes and alter the bathymetry of the Kardia mine, resulting in a pit that is 4.2 km long and 3.9 km wide, with elevations ranging from +523 m to +680 m above sea level (a.s.l.) and a maximum depth of 157 m.

In the context of the transition plan for the coal region, Land Repurposing Planning (LRP) for PPC includes the development of PV parks in the area surrounding the Kardia open pit. A complex of PV parks is foreseen to be implemented on the internal and external waste dumps and around the surface mine excavations (Fig. 1). The total power installed will be approximately 1000 MW_{peak}, capable of partially substituting the lignite power plants. Additionally, LRP focuses on agricultural and recreational developments in the area of the exhausted Kardia mine [36].

Within the framework of the project ATLANTIS [46], the most suitable area for the HPMS upper reservoir location within the mining licence boundaries was selected using a Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM) approach integrated with a Geographical Information System (GIS) for optimisation, as detailed in [60] (Fig. 1, right). Table 1 outlines the resulting system-related parameters and technical specifications.

2.2. Model for economic performance optimisation

Day-ahead electricity market prices — calculated and published in advance by power exchanges — alongside the residual load, offer valuable indicators for future planning and optimisation of energy systems. These data sources are particularly relevant for the operation of HPMS systems, which function as energy arbitrage systems by leveraging market dynamics and renewable generation patterns for efficient deployment. Energy-Charts [62] provides forecasts of the expected feed-in from renewable energy sources up to 72 h in advance, including wind and solar generation. This forecast data, when used in combination with market prices and residual load projections, enables the development of forward-looking strategies for HPMS scheduling, grid stability, and the mitigation of supply–demand imbalances. In this context, the forecasts offer a foundation for data-driven planning approaches that support the optimal integration of HPMS systems into increasingly volatile and decentralised electricity markets.

Three different time-dependent operation states of the HPMS system are considered for the generic design case: staying offline (idle mode), discharging (electricity generation; turbinning) and charging (energy storage; pumping). The schematic flowchart of the techno-economic model is presented in Fig. 2.

A set of criteria, based on the day-ahead electricity grid prices, their calculated average values for a 12-h period, and the available storage capacities in the upper reservoir, must be satisfied to trigger changes in the operational mode. Daily power auctions are conducted for each hour of the following day on the day-ahead market, with bids required to be submitted by noon at the respective exchange [63,64]. Energy production and spot market price data for the Greek energy market are based on hourly intervals and were obtained from [62].

Two criteria must be satisfied to maximise energy production through the use of water discharge from the upper reservoir:

- The potential energy stored in the upper reservoir is greater than zero (above the minimum storage level).

Fig. 2. Flowchart of the dynamic techno-economic HPHS model used to optimise the operational mode of the energy arbitrage system based on day-ahead grid prices and residual load.

Table 1
Site-specific technical characteristics and parameters.

Parameter		Value	Unit	References
P_{inst}	Installed capacity	130	MW	Optimised
Δh	Hydraulic head difference	86.45	m	Assumed
E_{stor}	Energy storage capacity ^a	1107	MWh	Calculated
N_{turb}	Number of Francis turbines	1	–	Assumed
$Q_{ch,max}$	Maximum flow rates for charging/pumping	131	m ³ /s	Calculated
$Q_{dis,max}$	Maximum flow rates for discharging/generating	138	m ³ /s	Calculated
η_{ch}	Efficiency of charging/pumping ^b	85.44	%	Wessel et al. [39]
η_{dis}	Efficiency of discharging/generating ^b	90.07	%	Wessel et al. [39]
$t_{ch,FL}$	Full-load hours for charging/pumping	9:57	h:min	Calculated
$t_{dis,FL}$	Full-load hours for discharging/generating	9:27	h:min	Calculated
L_{pen}	Penstock length	450	m	Krassakis et al. [60]
D_{pen}	Penstock diameter	6	m	Assumed
f	Friction factor	0.0149	–	Assumed
ρ	Density of water	1000	kg/m ³	Assumed
V_w	Working water volume	4.7	Mm ³	Schnepper et al. [38]

^a Based on the potential energy equation, the energy storage capacity is calculated using the hydraulic head difference, water density, gravitational acceleration, and working water volume ($E_{stor} = \Delta h \cdot g \cdot \rho \cdot V_w$).

^b Includes frictional head losses, calculated using the Darcy–Weisbach equation.

- The current day-ahead grid price must be higher than the average price within the current 12-h window.

Several conditions must be met to charge the upper reservoir of the HPHS system by pumping water into it. These conditions include:

- The current day-ahead electricity price must be lower than its average value within the 12-h window.
- The actual amount of residual load available in the grid must also be below its average value within the 12-h period (this is an optional criterion).

If these criteria are met, water will be pumped at maximum capacity, given that excess vRES are available (Section 2.3). In the absence of excess energy, the pumping capacity is proportionally adapted.

The stored and generated energy, as well as the revenues, expenditures, and profit produced after each HPHS operation step, are calculated based on the grid prices. The price spread is the average difference between the buying and selling price for one MWh of electricity in the reference year and derived from the modelling results on

the generated energy and profit. The higher the fluctuations on the day-ahead market for electricity, the higher the price spread and profit from storing and generating energy.

In the present study, two scenarios were investigated to evaluate their effects on energy storage and generation: “Grid price” (S1) and “Grid price and residual load” (S2). The “Grid price” (S1) scenario is defined by considering only the criteria related to the actual grid price, where prices are compared to the average value. This analysis determines whether energy should be stored (when the grid price is below the average) or generated (when the grid price is above the average) based on a comparison of the average hourly electricity price within a ± 12 -h time window against the actual grid price. In the second scenario, “Grid price and residual load” (S2), an additional condition requires the residual load to be below its average value to initiate energy storage. The residual load refers to the electricity demand not met by vRES and must be supplied by conventional power plants, imported electricity, or released stored energy. By considering the actual residual load, the scenario ensures a significant amount of excess vRES is available in the electricity market, optimising the HPHS pumping capacity. This additional criterion ensures that a high share of vRES is used for energy storage in the upper reservoir.

Fig. 3. Day-ahead electricity costs at the Greek energy market in 2023 [62].

Fig. 4. Residual load in the Greek electricity grid in 2023 [62]. Residual load refers to the amount of electricity demand that remains after accounting for the energy supplied by vRES.

Fig. 5. Solar power in the Greek electricity grid in 2023 [62].

The following discussion examines the application of the dynamic techno-economic model to historical data sets for the Greek energy market from 2015 to 2024.

2.3. Historical data of the Greek electric grid

Historical data sets were analysed for Greece to assess the economic feasibility of HPHS operation at the Greek Kardias Mine. The previously introduced techno-economic optimisation model was applied to hourly-discretised data sets, representative for the Greek energy market from 2015 to 2024. In this subsection, the input data Grid Price, Residual Load, Solar and Wind Power for 2023 are discussed in more detail as an example.

The analysis of the historical data sets (2015–2024) is given in Section 3.1. Figs. 3–6 exemplarily show the hourly data for the Greek

energy market in 2023 used for a detailed analysis of the characteristics of the day-ahead electricity costs, residual as well as onshore wind and solar energy loads [62].

Fig. 3 illustrates the 2023 development of the wholesale electricity costs in Greece, emphasising their high variation with maximum costs exceeding 350 €/MWh during certain time periods in January and August 2023. This highlights the fluctuations over a 12-h time period with daily price spreads of above 150 €/MWh. Peak costs specifically occur between 6–9 am and 5–9 pm.

Fig. 4 shows both the daily and annual fluctuations in the residual load. It varies by up to 40 GW throughout the day, with the lowest values generally occurring around noon when a high share of solar energy is fed into the grid. Usually, average electricity consumption is higher in the winter months than in summer, as people tend to

Fig. 6. Wind power in the Greek electricity grid in 2023 [62].

Fig. 7. Average operational time (dashed black line, in hours/year) and levelised profit (solid grey line, in €/kW) plotted as a function of installed capacity over a ten-year operational period (2015–2024).

spend more time at home, resulting in increased demand. However, high temperatures and the consequent use of air conditioning systems have altered these typical seasonal load curves during the summer of 2023. As a result, the highest residual loads for Greece in 2023 were observed during the evening hours of the summer season.

The high variation in solar power generation is illustrated in Fig. 5, where the time period from June to September represents the peak months, with loads reaching up to 5 GW.

The fluctuations in energy generation from onshore wind production in Greece in 2023 are plotted in Fig. 6. These are caused by shifts in weather patterns, which affect the wind speed. Typically, wind power production reaches its highest levels during the winter months, helping to balance the lower energy input from solar installations during this time of year. Wind power volatility also becomes evident during periods of reduced solar irradiance when the vast majority of power demand is met by conventional power plants. This increases grid costs, as seen in the first days of January 2023, with a subsequent drop in grid costs in mid-January, when wind energy production increased again (Fig. 3).

2.4. Model parametrisation

The dynamic economic model was applied to optimise an HPHS operation over a ten-year period (2015–2024) with varying installed

capacities ranging from 120 MW to 200 MW in 5 MW increments. During this period, total generated energy ranges from approximately 3700 GWh to 4800 GWh, while profit spans from about 95 M€ to 160 M€ as function of the installed capacity. The relationships between installed capacity, average operational time, and levelised profit are presented in Fig. 7. The average operational time per installed MW ranges from approximately 3500 to 2600 h/year, while levelised profit spans from about 800 €/kW to 840 €/kW as a function of installed capacity. The generated energy curve, representing technical efficiency, shows a monotonically decreasing trend. At low installed capacities, the HPHS operates nearly constantly, resulting in a high efficiency. However, the storage is charged and discharged more faster at high storage capacities, resulting in longer offline times per MW, ultimately decreasing efficiency. The profit curve, which represents the optimal economic scale, exhibits a distinct trend. For low installed capacities, the HPHS operates very efficiently, taking advantage of only the optimum grid price windows, resulting in high profits per MW. As installed capacity increases, the curve rises to a peak, representing the optimum between flexibility and volume, which is also the economic optimum in view of performance costs. Beyond this peak, additional installed capacities keep generating profits, but at a lower gain per MW, as less advantageous grid price windows are used, decreasing efficiency. This results in the concave profit coefficient curve.

Based on the application of the model and optimisation method to the parameter set in Table 1, an optimal installed capacity of 130 MW was determined for the current case study, representing the optimum balance between technical and economic efficiency. This capacity has been adopted for all subsequent simulation scenarios.

Table 1 outlines the resulting system-related parameters and technical specifications. The parameters used in the simulation model are indicative and can be adjusted based on the specific technical design and planning of the HPHS system.

For the HPHS facility in Greece, levelised CAPEX of approximately 1100 €/kW are assumed. These CAPEX and respective total investment costs of 143 M€ fall within the lower range for a representative 150 MW ‘Greenfield’ PHS project, reported by Giesecke et al. [26], and are consistent with the CAPEX range previously listed for comparable PHS projects. OPEX are based on empirical values from hydropower plants in operation and are assumed to be around 3%–5% p.a. of CAPEX. These can be further distinguished into 0.5–1.5% p.a. of the investment share related to construction costs and 2.5–3.5% p.a. attributable to electrical and mechanical equipment costs. The OPEX also account for maintenance-related expenditures on geological and civil infrastructure, including reservoirs, pipes and penstocks, buildings, electro-mechanical and electrical equipment, instrumentation and control systems, and general site services. This categorisation follows established definitions in the literature [26,46], where OPEX encompass operation, maintenance, and replacement costs across civil, hydraulic, and structural components. Additionally, approximately 1% of the CAPEX can be accounted for personnel expenditures [65]. Therefore, the OPEX used in the simulation model are 4% of CAPEX = 5.72 M€/year.

2.5. Economic evaluation

Criteria for assessing the economic feasibility of the HPHS implementation at the Kardia Mine include NPV, IRR, DPP, and LCOS. Using these metrics together provides a thorough evaluation of a project’s financial prospects. A positive NPV and an IRR above the interest rate indicate profitability. A reasonable DPP ensures investment recovery within an acceptable timeframe. Additionally, a competitive LCOS confirms the cost-effectiveness of the energy storage solution. Collectively analysing these indicators provides stakeholders with a comprehensive view of the project’s economic viability, enabling them to make informed investment decisions. In the following, the common methods used to evaluate the metrics are briefly introduced.

The NPV represents the total value of benefits and costs of a project by totalling all discounted net revenues, represented as B (€), over its lifecycle N (years), and comparing them with the initial investment costs C (€) at time $t = 0$ (years), considering an interest rate of r (%) (Eq. (1)). Interest rates may vary due to economic factors, central bank policies, and market demand [66,67]. For this study, considering an infrastructure project under the assumption of stable economic conditions, the interest rate is applied as 4.5%.

$$NPV = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(B - C)}{(1 + r)^n} \quad (1)$$

The IRR (Internal Rate of Return) is the interest rate r (%) that makes the NPV of a project’s cash flows equal to zero (Eq. (2)). It is defined as the value of r that satisfies the following equation:

$$NPV(r) = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{B_n}{(1 + r)^n} - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{C_n}{(1 + r)^n} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where B_n and C_n represent the benefit and cost cash flows in year n , respectively, and N is the project lifetime in years. The IRR represents the annualised return generated by the project over its lifetime and serves as an indicator of investment efficiency. However, since the IRR is sensitive to the distribution of cash flows over time, it should always be interpreted in conjunction with the NPV. Generally, an IRR above

10% indicates a favourable investment, while a return below 5% may prompt investors to reconsider their decision [68].

The *Discounted Payback Period* indicates the number of years it takes for an investment to break even, accounting for the present value of future cash flows (Eq. (3)). This involves discounting future cash flows (CF_n) and recognising the time value of money.

$$DPP = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(CF_n)}{(1 + r)^n} \quad (3)$$

LCOS is a simple, intuitive, and useful metric for determining whether a new energy storage plant would be profitable over its life cycle [69]. The LCOS method is derived from the Levelised Costs of Electricity (LCOE), which was developed to compare the cost of electricity from vRES with that from conventionally generated electricity [57,70]. Here, LCOS are used to evaluate and compare the cost of energy storage technologies for various applications [71,72]. LCOS (shown in Eq. (4)), take into account all expenses, including CAPEX and annual costs (A_t), divided by the total amount of energy discharged by the storage system (W_{out}) over its lifetime (N). Discounting is applied to both the annual costs and energy output to accurately assess the LCOS, taking into account the time factor and a discount factor (i). The annual costs include operational expenditures ($OPEX_t$), reinvestments in storage components ($CAPEX_{re,t}$), the amount of energy charged by the storage system per year (W_{in}), and the costs of purchasing electricity (Eq. (5)). Additionally, a recovery value (R_t) can be included for components that exceed the system’s intended lifespan. In the present study, the end-of-life cost is considered to be zero because the system has a long lifespan, and the recovery value is heavily discounted over this period, as noted by [57].

$$LCOS = \frac{CAPEX + \sum_{t=1}^N \frac{A_t}{(1+i)^t}}{\sum_{t=1}^N \frac{W_{out}}{(1+i)^t}} \quad (4)$$

$$A_t = OPEX_t + CAPEX_{re,t} + c_{el} \cdot W_{in} - R_t \quad (5)$$

3. Results and discussion

This section presents the outcomes of the techno-economic assessment and discusses the implications of the results for HPHS implementation. The analysis covers historical performance, the influence of operational time on key financial indicators, and the sensitivity of results to the identified economic risk factors. Additionally, the role of subsidies in enhancing financial viability is examined and a comparative analysis of LCOS with other storage technologies.

3.1. Analysis of historical performance

The techno-economic optimisation model was applied to ten hourly discretised data sets [62], representing the Greek energy market from 2015 to 2024. Fig. 8 exemplarily shows the simulated temporal storage level of the Greek HPHS system during the year 2024. The calculated profit of the Greek HPHS system for 2024 is approximately 21.90 M€, driven by the model criteria given in the ‘‘Grid price’’ scenario (S1).

Fig. 9 shows the variation of the storage level (blue) as a function of the day-ahead auction price (red) and its averaged value (green) for an exemplary week in June 2024. Purchased energy is used to recharge the upper reservoir when the electricity price falls below the average level, typically starting in the morning hours. Conversely, the upper reservoir is fully discharged and the generated electricity is supplied to the grid when the grid price exceeds the average level, usually during the evening hours.

The simulation results on generated energy profit and price spread for the two scenarios introduced above – ‘‘Grid price’’ (S1) and ‘‘Grid price and residual load’’ (S2) – applied to historical data for the years 2015–2024, are displayed in Table 2 and in Fig. 10.

Fig. 8. Simulation results for the 24-h averaged storage level of the upper reservoir and cumulative generated energy by the Kardia Mine HPHS system in 2024.

Fig. 9. Simulation results for the storage level (hourly) of the HPHS system as well as day-ahead auction and average prices for an exemplary week in June 2024.

Table 2

Simulated annual energy generation and profit from HPHS electricity sales, along with the associated total price spread, based on historical data sets for the Greek energy market from 2015 to 2024 for the investigated scenarios: “Grid price” (S1) and “Grid price and residual load” (S2).

Scenario	Grid price (S1)			Grid price and residual load (S2)		
	Generated energy (GWh)	Profit (M€)	Price spread (€/MWh)	Generated energy (GWh)	Profit (M€)	Price spread (€/MWh)
2015	372	2.74	7.37	349	2.78	7.96
2016	380	2.04	5.37	330	1.91	5.80
2017	384	4.38	11.42	355	4.12	11.61
2018	380	2.21	5.81	330	2.07	6.27
2019	379	3.83	10.10	342	3.70	10.81
2020	387	5.49	14.17	346	5.29	15.27
2021	403	13.18	32.71	368	12.38	33.65
2022	411	35.07	85.28	349	31.59	90.58
2023	403	18.15	45.05	332	16.64	50.14
2024	395	21.90	55.51	338	20.62	61.01
Average	389	10.90	27.28	344	10.11	29.31

Fig. 10. Comparison of annual generated energy and profits by the HPHS system at the Kardia Mine from 2015 to 2024 for the investigated scenarios: “Grid price” (S1) and “Grid price and residual load” (S2).

The modelling results for the first scenario, “Grid price” (S1), a steady increase in energy generation from 2015 to 2024, with slight drops in 2018 and 2019. The overall trend is positive and indicates a potential for growth and development of storage technologies in Greece, mainly driven by the ongoing build-out of national vRES.

The highest energy generation is calculated for 2022 with 411 GWh, followed by 2021 and 2023 with 403 GWh. The profits from HPHS electricity sales also show a positive trend, with a substantial increase from 2.74 M€ in 2015 to 35.07 M€ in 2022. The significant jump in potential profits in 2022 is a result of the war in Ukraine and the associated energy crisis, in which costs for electricity and natural gas drastically increased world-wide. The price spread is highly volatile, with yearly fluctuations. However, an overall increasing trend can be observed, which started in 2019 with the price spread reaching its peak in 2022. This change was primarily due to the increase in Greek vRES production and the decrease in contributions from fossil fuel-powered plants.

The modelling results for the second scenario, “Grid Price and Residual Load” (S2), over the investigated ten-year period, exhibit a similar trend for the profit but with reduced absolute values. The scenario consistently produced less energy per year due to the more selective operating strategy that restricts pumping to periods of high renewable availability.

The results indicate that the first strategy yields a slightly higher average annual profit of 10.90 M€ (compared to 10.11 M€ in the second scenario), accompanied by a higher average annual energy generation of 389 GWh (versus 344 GWh). However, the second scenario achieves a greater average price spread of 29.31 €/MWh, which is 7.45% higher than that of the first scenario (27.28 €/MWh). This increased price spread reflects a more selective and economically efficient operational strategy, enabling profitable operation with fewer operating hours. The reduced operational time associated with the second scenario suggests potential secondary benefits, including lower maintenance costs, reduced cumulative mechanical and hydraulic load on equipment, and improved overall lifecycle economics-factors not fully captured in the profit metric. Furthermore, the use of residual load as a control signal fosters better alignment with the availability of renewable energy, contributing to grid flexibility and sustainability goals. While the grid price-only strategy maximises energy throughput, the combined approach with residual load integration enhances operational efficiency and economic selectivity, making it a promising method for HPHS optimisation under dynamic market and energy system conditions.

The applied techno-economic simulation model offers a dynamic and transferable framework for evaluating the feasibility of HPHS, yet certain limitations remain. CAPEX and OPEX values are derived from literature and may not fully reflect site-specific geological, technical, or regulatory conditions. Particularly for repurposed lignite mines, uncertainties in long-term maintenance (e.g. reservoir sealing, structural stability) can affect cost accuracy. Further, the model uses historical day-ahead electricity market prices (2015–2024), allowing for robust retrospective analysis but offering limited forecasting due to market and policy uncertainties. Technical performance parameters, such as efficiency and availability, are based on idealised assumptions and may differ in real operations.

3.2. Impact of operational time on key performance criteria

The performance criteria NPV, IRR and DPP were first analysed as a function of input parameters that exhibit a high degree of fluctuation or uncertainty. Thereby, the effects of operational time on NPV, IRR, and DPP were determined by taking into account price spread variations.

Fig. 11 shows the NPV as a function of varying price spread. The HPHS system generates a positive NPV of 4.61 M€ at an average price spread of 38 €/MWh after 30 years of operation. This threshold decreases with increasing operational time, so that the system generates a positive NPV (2.28 M€) at an average price spread of 35 €/MWh after an operating time of 40 years. A price spread of approximately 34 €/MWh during an operating time of 50 years is sufficient to achieve a positive NPV (5.33 M€). The HPHS system would not be profitable if the average price spread of the past ten years (27.28 €/MWh) is considered. However, with an average price spread of around 55 €/MWh, calculated as the average of the last four years, all three scenarios result in a positive NPV of 112.33 M€, 145.44 M€, and 166.77 M€ over 30, 40, and 50 years of operation, respectively.

Fig. 12 shows the IRR as a function of varying price spread for positive NPVs. The longer the operational time, the higher the IRR, whereby these lines converge with the increase in price spread, and thus the NPV. This results from the IRR calculation, which is based on a constant annual cash-flow value and due to the fact that it discounts the future cash-flows to their present value. Considering the present modelling results, an IRR of 10% will be achieved at a price spread of approximately 71 €/MWh, resulting in an NPV of just above 213 M€.

Fig. 11. Impact of operational lifetime on the NPV at varying price spreads.

Fig. 12. Impact of operational lifetime on IRR at varying price spreads.

Based on the average price spread of 55 €/MWh over the previous four years, the calculated IRR for a 30-year operational period is 5.65%.

Fig. 13 illustrates how the DPP varies as a function of price spread in scenarios with positive NPVs, demonstrating that lower price spreads correspond to higher DPPs. The findings indicate that a DPP of less than 10 years can be achieved if the price spread exceeds 62 €/MWh, regardless of the overall operational lifetime.

3.3. Sensitivity analysis on the relevance of potential economic risks

A sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate how changes in key economic parameters affect the NPV. The scenarios and parameters examined include: “Capital Investment Impact” (CAPEX), “Energy Yield Variation” (generated energy), “Interest Rate Influence” (interest rate), “Operational Cost Adjustment” (OPEX), and “Operational Duration Effect” (operational time). In each scenario, the parameter values were varied by ±50% in ten incremental steps. The key parameters assessed in the sensitivity analysis include the CAPEX, assumed to be

143 M€; the annual energy yield, set to 389 GWh/year; the interest rate, considered with 4.5%; OPEX, estimated to 4% of CAPEX; and the operational lifetime of the project, assumed to be 30 years.

The results are presented in a spider diagram (Fig. 14). The robustness of these findings was assessed by stepwise adjustments to these parameters. The input parameters selected for this scenario analysis are considered conservative, given the daily fluctuations in electricity prices and the overall increase in potential energy generation by the HPHS during the simulated 2015–2024 period. These include an average annual energy price spread of 37.28 €/MWh and an average energy generation of 389 GWh. OPEX is defined as 4% of CAPEX and the interest rate set to 4.5%.

Annual savings of approximately 8.78 M€ and NPV of 0.04 M€ are projected over an operational lifetime of 30 years. In contrast, the average profit for the past ten years (2015–2024) was calculated to 10.90 M€ (neglecting OPEX). These values serve as the baseline parameters for the subsequent sensitivity scenario analysis.

Fig. 13. Impact of operational lifetime on DPP at different price spreads.

Fig. 14. Sensitivity of NPV to a ±50% variation in the economic key parameters, expressed as a percentage of CAPEX.

The sensitivity analysis results indicate that the generated energy and CAPEX are the most significant contributors to the NPV. Specifically, a 10% increase in generated energy can lead to a potential NPV increase of 16.55%, while a 10% decrease in CAPEX can result in a potential NPV increase of 16.55%. In the present analysis, the total range of fluctuations in generated energy is considered substantial. A 50% increase, as an example, represents a scenario in which the HPHS operates at full capacity throughout the entire year, with minimal idle hours. Meanwhile, the fluctuations observed in the simulated HPHS operation, based on historical data from 2015 to 2024, deviate from the average value by approximately +5.4% and -4.4%, respectively. A decrease in the interest rate by 10% corresponds to an increase of 5.55% in NPV, and a 10% decrease in OPEX results in a 6.55% increase in the NPV. A 10% prolongation of operational time, which is equivalent to a three-year extension in the given scenario, leads to an NPV increase of approximately 4.54%. Additionally, the sensitivity analysis results indicate that the key economic parameters leading to a negative impact on NPV include reduced energy generation, potentially

decreasing NPV by 16.49%, and higher CAPEX, which could also reduce NPV by 16.48% with a 10% variation. A 10% increase in interest rates corresponds to a 5.05% reduction in NPV, while a 10% rise in OPEX leads to a 6.48% decrease in NPV. Furthermore, a 10% reduction in operational time results in approximately a 5.11% decrease in NPV.

Recent studies on PHS in closed open-pit and subsurface mines, such as Wessel et al. [39], Saha et al. [41], and Madlener and Specht [42], also highlight CAPEX as the dominant factor for NPV and project feasibility. Saha et al. [41] show that specific investment costs decline from 2860 USD/kW (56 MW) to 1552 USD/kW (353 MW), demonstrating strong economy of scale effects. Wessel et al. [39] report CAPEX values of 600–3000 €/kW with a representative figure of about 1726 €/kW, and link costs to installed power and reservoir size. Madlener and Specht [42] emphasise that in subsurface mines, construction and engineering dominate CAPEX, underscoring the connection to installed capacity.

The structured economic risk assessment includes 43 site-specific risks, with financial impacts estimated via sensitivity analysis — relying

on assumptions that may affect outcomes. The model also assumes ideal grid access and dispatch flexibility, potentially overstating revenues by not accounting for real-world constraints like curtailment or congestion.

3.3.1. Economic risks associated with “Capital Investment Impact”

The economic risks linked to changes in CAPEX for the HPHS system include factors such as location-specific tax rate fluctuations and increases in both CAPEX and OPEX due to potential interest rate changes. An increase in both tax and interest rates ultimately leads to higher costs during the construction phase, thereby raising the total required investment. A 5% rise in CAPEX leads to a 8.3% reduction in NPV, approximately equating to 11.8 M€. Similarly, a 20% increase in CAPEX results in a nearly 33% reduction in NPV, which corresponds to roughly 47.2 M€.

3.3.2. Economic risks associated with “Energy Yield Variation”

One major risk is the decreasing costs of other storage technologies, becoming economically competitive with HPHS. Such a technological development could potentially result in a decrease in demand for HPHS, leading to lower production and potentially affecting the overall profitability of the system. Unfavourable changes in national legislation, particularly in terms of subsidies and energy-related directives, can also pose a significant risk to HPHS installations. Moreover, a reduction in storage capacity caused by sedimentation or increased evaporation due to climate change can increase the maintenance and operational costs of the upper reservoir. Sediment accumulation in EU reservoirs exceeds 1 billion m³ annually, with estimated removal costs between 5 and 8 billion €, highlighting the economic burden of reservoir maintenance due to soil erosion [73]. When the storage capacity is diminished, less water can be stored, resulting in a decrease in potential energy available for electricity generation. This can lead to reduced revenue from energy production. Additionally, the reservoir may require more frequent pumping operations to maintain adequate water levels, which increases energy consumption and operational expenses as pumps need to operate more often. Furthermore, general atmospheric risks such as storms and extreme events can result in power grid outages, affecting the system’s overall efficiency and profitability. The economic risks associated with HPHS extend beyond energy-related factors: changes in regional flood protection plans, industrial underdevelopment, and periods of unexpectedly low electricity demand — particularly during times of surplus supply — can reduce operational revenues and lead to temporary financial losses. Analysis of the historical data from the past ten years (2015–2024) indicates that variations in grid costs and residual load can result in an energy generation variation of approximately 6%. For a scenario with a 37.28 €/MWh price spread, a 1% reduction in energy production (3.89 GW) would result in a 2.3 M€ decrease in NPV, while a 15% reduction would lead to a decrease in NPV of 35.4 M€, rendering the project economically unviable. In the latter case, an average price spread of at least 43 €/MWh would be required for the HPHS system to remain profitable after 30 years. The greatest risk is posed by declining costs of alternative energy storage systems. The latest trends suggest that battery storage systems, in particular, may become competitive in view of HPHS, although they are typically designed for shorter storage periods and lower storage capacities. Studies show that besides the fast development of battery storage technology, PHS will remain a key technology for energy storage at high capacities [14]. According to International Energy Agency [3], the global PHS capacity is anticipated to extend by 7% to 9 TWh until 2030. With this development, pumped storage capacity will remain higher than that of batteries including electric vehicles.

3.3.3. Economic risks associated with “Interest Rate Influence”

Economic risks associated with interest rate increases can significantly impact CAPEX and OPEX. A relative increase in the interest rate by 50%, raising it to an absolute rate of 6.75%, would require an average price spread of around 43 €/MWh to achieve a positive NPV.

3.3.4. Economic risks associated with “Operational Cost Adjustment”

OPEX risks can be attributed to a number of potential events, such as the partial repair of damage to the powerhouse or upper reservoir, unexpected high inflation rates during operation, slope stability monitoring, ground surface subsidence, groundwater monitoring, groundwater contamination, and necessary remediation and water treatment measures. The risks are primarily characterised by the fact that they involve additional investment, which can also be considered as a negative cash flow, either for specific years or throughout the entire operational time of the HPHS. Therefore, variations in OPEX are taken into account to reflect these additional investments. According to Giesecke et al. [26] as well as Thema and Thema [65], OPEX vary between 3%–6% of CAPEX for “Greenfield” PHS systems. Considering a scenario with relatively high OPEX, calculated to 6% of the CAPEX, any partial repair costs are likely to result in a 2% increase in OPEX, raising it to 8% of the CAPEX. In this case, the average price spread must be at least 52 €/MWh to achieve a positive NPV over the operational lifetime.

3.3.5. Economic risks associated with “Operational Duration Effect”

Potential economic risks associated with decreases in operational time can vary greatly. These risks are primarily related to geotechnical failures of the slopes in the lower reservoir, as well as their maintenance, stabilisation, and potential reconstruction in case of failure. Additionally, changes in EU/national energy directives can result in unforeseen interruptions of operation. This may be further compounded by changes in regional water management plans, leading to a loss of operating time and insufficient replenishment to compensate for evaporation, resulting in a longer payback period. There is also potential for partial repairs of the penstock, decreased precipitation, and loss of operating time due to a lack of materials for construction and maintenance. Additional risks may include turbine and penstock clogging due to incrustation, as well as material embrittlement. There may also be extra costs associated with artificial recharge, such as obtaining permits and paying water usage fees. Consideration should also be given to regional flood protection plans, which may impact the operational time of HPHS systems. All these mentioned risks could decrease operational time by causing downtimes. Changes in regional water management plans could lead to the upper reservoir becoming unavailable for storage if there is insufficient water in the lower reservoir, potentially causing an operational shutdown for several months. Additionally, any risks that necessitate maintenance activities can significantly reduce operational time. In HPHS systems, replacement work and/or partial repairs usually take several weeks, unlike unplanned maintenance, and could result in downtimes spanning multiple months or even years. Geotechnical stability is essential for the continuous and safe operation, as failures may lead to extended downtimes. Liu et al. [74] show that fluctuating reservoir water levels can adversely affect slope stability, increasing the risk of landslides under specific hydrological conditions.

3.4. Relevance of subsidies to ensure security of energy supply

Subsidies for energy storage systems require an evaluation in the context of the HPHS implementation at the Kardia Mine. Currently, subsidies for vRES significantly impact energy prices, competition, and market structure [75]. The term “subsidy” covers a variety of measures in discussions, which can differ depending on their effect, sector, and purpose. Country-specific subsidies could lead to a more favourable buying price, resulting in a higher price spread for the HPHS operator, which would further improve the overall HPHS economics. European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy et al. [75] has identified five categories and 26 instruments for energy subsidies. The findings show a recent increase in energy subsidies across the EU, with vRES receiving the most support compared to other energy sources. While open-pit HPHS has high potential for energy storage, it alone is insufficient to enable a shift to 100% renewable electricity. Countries

Fig. 15. LCOS for two OPEX scenarios depending on the yearly energy discharge, considering a discount factor of 8% and an annual reinvestment of an additional 1% of CAPEX, excluding the costs of electricity.

will likely need to incorporate systems such as “Greenfield” and “Blue-field” PHS, saltwater PHS using the ocean as a lower reservoir, or seasonal storage linked to major rivers to achieve this goal [17,32]. When considering the implementation of HPHS at mining sites, it is important to take into account factors such as water quality, unstable pit slopes, and environmental regulations, as well as potential land usage limitations [36]. Liu et al. [33] concluded from their study of an undisclosed open-pit iron mine that incorporating PHS into mine planning could yield both financial and environmental benefits. They emphasised that this approach can optimise efficiency and enhance both financial returns and environmental sustainability.

3.5. Levelised cost of storage and comparison with other energy storage options

Assuming an average annual energy output for the HPHS system (W_{out}) of 389 GWh, and taking into account additional parameters — including a reinvestment in storage components ($CAPEX_{\text{re},i}$) of 1% CAPEX, a recovery value (R_r) of 0 €, a discount factor (i) of 8% [57], and a 30-year lifetime (N) - the project’s LCOS can be adequately assessed. Following Jülch [57], c_{el} is set to 0 €/kWh to ensure comparability between different storage technologies, independent of electricity purchase costs. Consequently, the LCOS calculation is based solely on the annual energy output W_{out} . Based on these factors and using Eq. (4), the corresponding LCOS is 0.054 €/kWh for an OPEX scenario of 4% CAPEX and 0.061 €/kWh for a 6% one.

In the LCOS of the HPHS system, based on the applied data for an OPEX scenario of 4% of CAPEX, the distribution of the main cost components is as follows: 65.74% is allocated to CAPEX, 27.41% to OPEX, and 6.85% to reinvestments. Fig. 15 illustrates the LCOS as a function of the yearly energy discharge for OPEX scenarios of 4% and 6% of CAPEX, excluding the costs of electricity. As the amount of annually discharged energy decreases, the LCOS increase significantly because the same CAPEX and annual costs are allocated to a smaller quantity of discharged energy. Values exceeding 1 €/kWh are not shown in the graph.

The cost analysis conducted by Jülch [57] is based on an operation consisting of 365 cycles per year, which equates to approximately 150 GWh annually produced energy. PHS systems exhibit the lowest costs, ranging from 0.05 to 0.09 €/kWh, while CAES systems range from 0.07

to 0.12 €/kWh. Among the three types of battery storage systems investigated, the LCOS varies more widely: lithium-ion batteries range from 0.23 to 0.37 €/kWh, lead–acid (Pb) batteries from 0.15 to 0.19 €/kWh, and vanadium redox flow batteries from 0.32 to 0.36 €/kWh. Mugyema et al. [71] compared the LCOS of different energy storage systems — linear electric machine-based gravity energy storage system, flywheel, lead–acid battery, lithium-ion battery, and vanadium-redox flow battery — for use in primary response applications, which involve rapidly providing or absorbing power to stabilise the grid frequency in response to short-term fluctuations in electricity supply and demand. In their study, the flywheel system emerged as the most competitive, with an LCOS ranging from approximately 0.1008 to 0.2916 €/kWh. As noted by Mugyema et al. [71], despite advancements in battery technologies, they continue to face the major challenge of a limited lifespan, particularly under conditions that demand a high number of annual cycles. In the study conducted by Comello and Reichelstein [76], the LCOS for lithium-ion batteries was estimated to be 0.085 €/kWh for an optimally sized system. According to BloombergNEF’s annual lithium-ion battery price surveys [77], battery prices have generally been decreasing in recent years due to technological advancements, economies of scale in manufacturing, and declining raw material costs. However, the resulting LCOS range of 0.054–0.061 €/kWh aligns with the literature, indicating that HPHS is a cost-effective option for utility-scale electricity storage. This competitiveness is attributed to PHS’s long lifespan and its ability to support numerous technically and economically feasible annual cycles, despite relatively high initial investment costs [57].

The LCOS per kWh might not fully capture the value of storage applications, particularly for long-term options where capacity-based remuneration could be more appropriate. Additionally, storage technologies provide essential features such as uninterrupted power supply and black start capabilities, which the LCOS method cannot adequately assess [57].

4. Conclusions

The present study presents a techno-economic analysis of a potential HPHS installation at the Kardia Mine in Greece, utilising a dedicated mathematical model. The analysis of historical energy data shows positive trends in energy generation and profits for the planned HPHS realisation. Even with the conservative assumptions applied here, the Kardia HPHS project can achieve a positive NPV, breaking even at

an average annual energy price spread of 37.28 €/MWh, considering specific values of the simulation model parameters. As the renewable energy market continues to grow, HPHS systems stand to benefit from high capacity utilisation. They can store surplus energy and release it when market prices rise above purchase costs, effectively offsetting conventional energy production. Additionally, the increase in renewable installations will boost the workload and overall capacity of HPHS, leading to greater energy generation by the system. According to the modelling results, the implementation of the HPHS at the Kardia Mine is expected to provide significant economic benefits.

The conducted sensitivity scenario analysis underscores the critical importance of managing CAPEX during the design phase to ensure the successful implementation of the HPHS project. Additionally, unexpected increases in inflation rates and maintenance costs during operation present significant economic risks. The scenarios examined with respect to inflation rate and OPEX increases reveal the price spreads required to achieve a positive NPV, highlighting the necessity of robust risk management in the realisation of HPHS projects.

In conclusion, the techno-economic assessment of the prospective HPHS implementation at the Greek Kardia Mine has shown promising economic benefits for the specific study area. The performance analysis of historical energy data indicates a positive trend in energy generation and profitability. Over a 10-year analysis of data for the targeted study site, combined with specific technical implementation parameters and intentionally conservative assumptions, this study illustrates that the economic benefits of implementing HPHS systems are reliable and consistent with real-world conditions, despite the model's simplifications. The growth of vRES is expected to persist, gradually supplanting conventional energy production in the mid-term, reflecting the upward trend observed over the past decade (2015–2024) in the EU. Consequently, the energy market will experience significant daily, weather-dependent, and seasonal fluctuations in both the proportion of renewables in the total energy mix and grid costs. An HPHS system stands to benefit from these fluctuations due to its higher capacity utilisation.

In this context, further research is needed to investigate and validate the economic benefits and potential performance optimisations of deploying multiple HPHS systems in energy markets. Specifically, it is crucial to quantify how utility-scale HPHS deployment and multi-system coordination can create self-regulating effects by systematically capping price peaks and narrowing price spreads, thereby impacting storage profitability. Future studies should also focus on integrating HPHS with other energy storage technologies, particularly battery systems. Such research should examine the feasibility and impact of integrated HPHS-battery installations to explore how these technologies can enhance each other's capabilities. Additionally, investigations should assess the potential of HPHS for peak shaving and load balancing within national energy grids, both independently and in conjunction with other storage technologies. It is important to determine the feasibility of HPHS to generate revenue through involvement in various energy market segments, in comparison to and collaboration with other storage solutions. Furthermore, necessary policy frameworks to unlock HPHS's unique value, especially in coal transition regions where infrastructure can be repurposed, should be developed. Comparative analysis of HPHS against other storage technologies is also critical, focusing on long-duration storage, grid stability contributions, and overall system cost-effectiveness.

Based on the current study's findings, HPHS is likely to offer a profitable energy storage solution not only in Greece, but also in wider EU countries and beyond. The technologies' black start capability provides more than simply the ability to store large amounts of electric energy to support the transition to renewable sources. Its black start capability and potential for extended storage capacities during Dunkelflaute periods make it a crucial element in securing the EU's energy supply. Along with the economic benefits identified in this study, these strategic advantages underscore the importance of

integrating HPHS plants into the EU's energy generation and storage framework. Additionally, incentives should be established to ensure the adoption of the HPHS technology in exhausted open-pit lignite mines, such as implementing feed-in tariffs and policies for using transitioning mining regions for utility-scale energy storage.

The proposed approach is flexible and transferable, with adjustable parameters such as CAPEX, OPEX, and site-specific design inputs, allowing application to other locations and evolving market conditions. However, the accuracy of the results depends on the quality of input data, particularly cost estimates. While the current model uses historical market data and a simple moving average, future work could improve operational scheduling by integrating advanced forecasting or optimisation methods, such as AI-based strategies based on day-ahead electricity prices.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Christopher Otto: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Georgios Louloudis:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Christos Roumpos:** Writing – review & editing. **Eleni Mertiri:** Writing – review & editing. **Priscilla Ernst:** Writing – review & editing. **Thomas Kempka:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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